

WHAT ARE THE MAIN STEPS OF A PROFESSIONAL FACIAL?

People demand facials for different reasons such as some want to remove horrible blackheads, some want only for relaxation purposes, and while others want anti-aging treatment. If you want benefits regarding [facial aesthetics](#), you can move to the near spa center.

A facial includes a multi-step skin treatment to take care of your skin. A facial helps your skin nourish properly. It cleanses, exfoliates, and promotes clear well-hydrated skin to look younger. You can ask for some skin-care tips to get the best ways to take care of your skin at home. This will help you to get facial enhancement near me.

You should always consult an experienced, knowledgeable licensed esthetician who has special training in skincare and is passionate about their work. It is a trend now to get services from a dual licensed professional so that you can get both of the services like massages and facial treatments as well. You can visit a resort providing both services at the same time. You can get the best services at a facial spa in Boston.

What are the basic steps of a facial?

Discussion regarding the treatment:

If you are planning to get a facial, you should share your skin health history with your professional at the [facial spa near me](#) such as on what medications you are so that he/she can consult you the suitable treatments not affecting your health much. For example, if you are using Retin-A, the esthetician will ask about your skin concerns before recommending any kind of treatment.

Once you have decided on the treatment, the esthetician will ask you to wrap your body and underneath your arms then closes with velcro.

Cleansing:

The esthetician will wrap your hair with a headband to apply the products to your face. During the process of cleansing, she will use cotton pads to wipe your face or she may use sponges to perform the procedure. Most estheticians do facials with a double-cleanse.

Treatment according to your skin type:

The estheticians will determine your basic skin type whether it is oily, dry, sensitive, normal, or combination, and skin conditions like if you have acne, blackheads, whiteheads, aging,

sun-damage, dehydration, etc through a bright magnified light. Then he/she will choose the appropriate products and treatments.

Steam:

Most facials are done using a steamer that sprinkles a thin vapor of warm steam to your face. The process helps soften up blackheads and whiteheads so that they can be easily eliminated. If your skin type is sensitive, they will not include this process.

Exfoliation:

This procedure includes mechanical or chemical substances. Mechanical exfoliants contain a rough texture that helps remove dead skin cells. This type of exfoliation is used generally during the steam. Whereas a chemical exfoliation involves enzymes and acids to loosen the bond amid skin cells. The esthetician may include a gentle enzyme treatment during the steam.

Extractions:

This process includes the elimination of blackheads or whiteheads if you need to get it done. This process may cause pain and discomfort for some people.

Facial mask:

A mask is applied according to your skin type meanwhile you can get a scalp massage also to let you relax.

If you want to enhance your face beauty, you can get facial spa treatments to make your appearance better and attractive.